

Pakistan's Brick Kilns: The Zig-Zag Efficiency

Author Details: Muhammad Saad Khurram

Aitchison College, Lahore, Pakistan.

Abstract:

This paper is based on the determination of Zig-Zag efficiency of a brick kiln company. All the factors of zig-zag technology are mentioned and studied keenly. The zig-zag technology in Okara, Punjab is examined for its emission factor that analysis. The data on input along with output prices and quantity shows it to be considered as good for health. The results of the study show that the zig-zag technology shows that it is environmentally friendly. It is also economical as compared to other technologies like Bull's Trench Kiln. Zigzag technology is also cost benefitting. It is proved that zig-zag technology is both social and private welfare technology.

Keywords: Brick kilns

Introduction:

With rapid growth and urbanization, the brick industry of Pakistan is at its boom growth rate. In Southeast Asia, Pakistan is the 3rd largest bricks producer after China and India. Pakistan has almost 11,500 brick kilns out of which, 10,000 are situated in Punjab. These brick kilns consume around 1.6 million tons of coal for the production of 45 billion bricks every year.^{1, 2} With the emerging awareness regarding the importance of environmental cleanness, many states have converted their brick production towards cleaner methods, however, Pakistan is lagging in modernizing its conventional kiln technology. The study has shown that the old Bull's Trench Kiln technology causes more pollution than new kiln technologies like Draft Zig-Zag Kiln (ZZK). These modern technologies provide a window of opportunity for environmental mitigation, enhancing air quality, and are cost-efficient. It is proven that Pakistan is at an alarming stage of high emission of gases.^{3, 4, 5}

Kilns are a source of Carcinogens.^{6, 7, 8} The ash of the kiln can contaminate agriculture.^{9, 10, 11} As Punjab, Pakistan has the highest number of brick kilns, the inquiries present the estimated amount of emission from these kilns as CO, CO₂, and Pm_{2.5} in the range between 2.5 – 3.9 megatons (mt), 120 – 127 megatons mt, and 0.20 mt, respectively. These kilns emit high levels of sulfur and ash contents as well. Other emitted particulate matter includes nitrogen oxide, ozone, methane, and black carbons. Currently, the conventional brick kilns burn cheap waste materials like plastics, discarded tires, and garbage as fuel, which in turn release the harmful poisonous byproducts directly into the air. These kilns are also a source of carcinogenic particulates like polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and other volatile organic compounds, which makes the environment of the brick production site far more threatening for the workers. Moreover, the disposal of kiln ash is composed of heavy metals and toxic compounds which can, in turn, contaminate agricultural areas and livestock.

On the other hand, ZZK technology has proved environmentally friendly. Recent surveys from India and Nepal have depicted that ZZK produces up to 70% fewer emissions in comparison to conventional kilns. The less emission ratio encapsulated all the harmful toxicants like Pm_{2.5}, SO₂, CO₂, CO. In addition, the economic analysis revealed that the shift from conventional method to modern proved fruitful for both, private and social welfare sector. Moreover, ZZK provides owners to recover their initial investment phases in 1.5 years in comparison to BTK, where it takes owners 2.5 years to recover their early investments. This paper encapsulates our findings regarding the acquisition of modern ZZK technology in Punjab, Pakistan; the environmental impacts (cleanness of ZZKs); economic and social perks of ZZKs in comparison to conventional kilns.

The paper focuses on the efficiency, heat transfer improvement, and environmental factors of zig-zag technology. Several samples were collected and analyzed from the newly developed kiln according to zig-zag technology in Okara. The owner of this kiln developed this kind of technology after analyzing several plans from International Center for Integrated Mountain Development. The evidence shows that this is the only developed kiln present in Punjab according to the zig-zag procedure. To find out the efficiency of this kiln, we

collected samples from different areas to find out the cost-effectiveness and other friendly behavior of this kiln technology as compared to the other kiln technologies. The prices, qualities, and quantities were compared to find out the results of this new technology. It is found that the zig-zag technology emits fewer amounts of SO₂, CO, CO₂, and PM₅ as compared to the other technologies. This shows that this technology is quite environmentally friendly and efficient. This reduced the burden of dangerous gases from the surroundings and help in the maintenance of a better environment for the people working there as well other communities.

Technologies of Brick Kiln:

Numerous technologies are helpful in the development of brick kiln industries. The most extensively used technology in Pakistan is the Bull's Trench Kiln technology. Normally, a BTK makes fifty thousand bricks in a day. This type of kiln makes a large chamber where several green bricks are baked. For baking, the fixed chimney having a height of twenty to thirty meters is designed in such a manner that it allows the draft gases to come towards the kiln and removes the waste gases. The green bricks are just the sun-dried clay molds. This chamber comprises three areas namely firing area, preheating area, and cooling area. In the firing area, combustion happens. This combustion makes the flue gas, which then flows towards the preheating area and it then heats the next batch of green bricks.

Prompt Draught Zig-zag Kiln:

The organization of zig-zag is the same as compared to the BTK. The difference between them is that they have a smaller chimney and there is a presence of an electric fan in the chimney to manage the flow of air through the chimney. The workers of this zigzag technology kiln diagonally manage the bricks all along with the chamber. This way increases the longer path for the air to flow through it. The longer the path of flow of air through the brick the better will be the efficiency of the kiln. This is the reason that the zig-zag kiln is efficient than other kilns. It has a greater fuel combustion efficiency than the BTK. Zig-zag technology also transfers more heat to the heating area from the preheating area. This process causes the consistent flow of air. The way of the flow of fuel gasses makes it environmentally friendly. The particulate materials are gathered on the bottom of the kiln which reduces the number of particles in the environment making the surroundings better for everyone.

Environmental Analysis:

Method:

Selection of Area:

We gathered the samples of emission from the zig-zag kiln present near Okara. It was constructed the half-year before the collection of samples and it was the only working kiln of that time functioning in this way. The other kilns work on the natural flow of air however, the zig-zag kiln has a fan that circulates the air in the kiln. The major source of emission and pollution is the kiln in our country. Agriculture and vehicles are the other sources of pollution.

Sampling and Source of Fuel:

The kilns operate on coal. In Pakistan, the major source of fuel is coal. The BTK utilizes two types of coals namely Hyderabad's in 3/4th proportion and Baluchistan's coal in 1/4th proportion. The coal of Baluchistan is better than the coal of Hyderabad. It is also more costly than Hyderabad coal. We collected the samples from all the kilns and analyzed them in the laboratory. We used proximate and ultimate analysis techniques. The proximate analysis shows the chemical content present in the kiln. It includes ash, moisture, and volatile content. The proximate analysis provides the calorific value. The ultimate analysis explains the contents of elements present in the coal. These include hydrogen, nitrogen, sulfur, and carbon, etc.

A sampling of Emission:

We calculated the emission of CO₂, NO_x, SO₂, CO, and the particles passing through the kiln. The zigzag kiln has a stack standing at the height of 12 meters while the BTK stack was at the height of 10 meters. We followed the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) guidelines for stack concentration to consider its effect on the concentration of emission.

Factors of Emission:

We measured the emission factors. The normalization of emission for each kiln allows us to compare numerous kilns with different sizes and technologies.

Researchers use emission factor data from every kiln in the country and estimate total emission of every kiln and compare them to find out required emission factor. This information is helpful in finding out the contribution of kiln in environmental analysis. The emission factor is calculated on two basis, one is energy mass based and the other one is fuel mass based. The energy mass based analysis shows the emission of pollutants per energy unit used. The fuel mass based calculates the emission of pollutant particles per unit of fuel mass used.

Both of these factors are derived from two equations/formulas. One is emission rate and the other one is consumption rate. The rate of emission (g/h) is as follows:

$$ER = 0.001 * S * Q_s$$

Here, S= concentration of emission (mg/m³), Q_s is the rate of flow of stack emission (m³/h).

The emission factor based on fuel mass *EF_m* (g/kg) is as follows:

$$EF_m = ER, \text{ where } F \text{ is the fuel consumption rate (kg/h).}$$

The emission factor based on energy mass *EF_e* (g/MJ) is as follows:

$$EF_e = EF_m E, \text{ where } EC \text{ is the content of fuel energy (MJ/kg).}$$

Result:

Analysis of Fuel:

These tables 1 and 2 show the proximate and ultimate analysis. The samples of coal were collected from the zig-zag and BTK. Zig-zag coal uses Baluchistan and BTK utilizes a mixture of coals from Hyderabad and Baluchistan. In this way, the zig-zag kiln seems to be the best option of the kiln which is efficient and environmentally better.

Table 1: Proximate Approximation of Samples of Coal

Sample	Ash (%)	Moisture (%)	GCV (MJ/kg)	VM (%)
Baluchistan-Hyderabad Mixture	20	10	23	31
Baluchistan	14	4	27	46
Hyderabad	12	4	19	39

Table: 2 Ultimate Approximation of Sample of Coal

Sample	Hydrogen	Sulfur	Carbon	Nitrogen
Baluchistan-Hyderabad Mixture	4	3	51	1.0
Baluchistan	5	6	69	1.2
Hyderabad	6	7	58	1.7

Stack Emission:

All the results show that the zig-zag kiln produces a fewer amount of gasses namely carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, and sulfur dioxide. The zig-zag kiln uses more oxygen in the feeding cycle. The emission of all kinds of gasses except NO_x is the same in all kinds of kilns statistically. The emission of NO_x from BTK (NF) is higher than the zigzag and BTK (K).

Emission Factors:

Table 3 shows the fuel-based and energy-based emission factors. It presents the emission factors for Zig-zag and BT Kiln. These normalizations represent the consistent comparison of both the kilns. BTK has a considerably greater emission factor for all gasses despite NO_x as compared to Zigzag kilns.

Table 3: Emission Rates and Emission Factors

Emission Type	Fuel based Emission Factor g/MJ		Energy based Emission Factor g/kg		Emission Rate g/h	
	ZZK	BTK	ZZK	BTK	ZZK	BTK
PM	0.9	43	0.05	1.9	300	9010
CO ₂	2900	8555	105	400	650,000	1,807,888
NO _x	1.9	1.5	0.08	0.07	400	300
CO	28	230	1.0	10.0	7000	50,000
SO ₂	8	300	0.4	13	1900	63000

Economic Analysis:

Private Costs

The starting capital costs for Zig-Zag Kiln consist of the down payment for advanced labor, land lease, equipment costs, wages, and construction. A lot of kiln owners in Pakistan make kilns with down payment at start. They also give advance payment for the workers to work in their kiln for specific period of time. This payment is paid back by the workers by working for their determined period of time. The cost of construction consists of expenditures on labor and material to erect the kiln. The zig-zag kiln has greater land cost as it requires greater area. It is calculated that zig-zag kiln has 9 Million more initial expenditures than the other kilns. It has greater labor costs and land costs. Zig-zag Kiln requires additional devices to operate which takes more investment. The electric fan, generator, connection of electricity and coal crusher costs for more money. The annual cost is divided into fixed and variable cost. The land lease is a fixed cost and the other expenditures like electricity, coal and fuel are the variable costs. Zig-zag kilns use high quality coal that why this kiln is expensive as compared to the other ones. Calculations show that zig-zag kilns use 33% less coal as compared to other kilns working in Pakistan.

The BTK and zig-zag kiln both emit a significant amount of carbon dioxide as is evident from the analysis. The cost of emission of carbon dioxide analyzed using the price of carbon dioxide and global trading markets gives the average of its whole cost.

The specific energy usage of coal for all kiln types is given by:

$$SEC^C = GCV^C * C^C / W$$

Here GCV^C stands for gross calorific value and C^C stands for coal consumption. W is the weight of the coal. GCV^C has a standard value of 25.7 MJ/kg. To find out the emission of carbon dioxide, following formula is used.

$$E_{CO_2} = CF_{CO_2} \times EF_e \times SEC \times Q$$

It is found out that the zig-zag kiln was as economic as half of the other kiln costs.

Conclusion:

It has been seen in the whole analysis that the zig-zag technology is more environmentally friendly and is socially cost-effective. The sample of our study used in zig-zag technology was lesser in amount as compared to the other technologies. The emission analysis shows that the zig-zag technology emitted a lesser amount of carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide as compared to other ones. The use of high-quality coal in this type of kiln makes it eco-friendly. All of the above pros make the zig-zag technology suitable as well as profitable for its owner.

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